

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Risky sexual behavior associated with accident causation among commercial vehicle drivers in Jalingo Metropolitan, Taraba State, Nigeria

Muhammad Zaharadeen Yahaya* and Shamsudeen Abubakar

Department of Physical and Health Education, Federal University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

The study investigated the risky sexual behaviours associated with accident causation among commercial vehicle drivers in Jalingo Metropolitan, Taraba State. The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population was 2,000 commercial vehicle drivers registered with National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) proportional sampling technique was used to sample 160 commercial vehicle drivers. Out of 160 copies of the questionnaire administered, 148 copies of questionnaires were returned for data analysis. The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Risky sexual behaviours are detrimental to wellbeing ($\bar{x} = 3.43$, $SD = .54$), followed by, long distances increase vulnerability to risky sexual behaviour among drivers ($\bar{x} = 3.38$, $SD = .55$), ogling and romancing while driving promote distractions among drivers ($\bar{x} = 3.32$, $SD = .52$) while, it makes driver vulnerable to sexual infections ($\bar{x} = 3.30$, $SD = .55$) and the least score of ($\bar{x} = 3.26$, $SD = .50$) was by, risky sexual behaviour causes loss of attention among drivers.

Keywords: Risky sexual behavior; Accident; Causation; Commercial Vehicle; Driver

1. Introduction

Risky sexual behaviour is yet health risk behaviour among drivers. Roughgarden (2004) defined sexual behaviour as the manner in which human experience and express their sexuality. The author further stated that people engage in variety of sexual acts from time to time for a variety of reasons which include, for fun and sexual satisfaction. Naturally, sexual arousal and physiological changes in the aroused person are results of sexual activity. On the other hand, Agnw (2007) defined risky sexual behaviour as behaviour that increases one's risk of contracting sexually transmitted infections and experiencing unintended pregnancies for the female. Risky sexual behaviour include; having sex at early age, having multiple sexual partners, having sex under the influence of alcohol or drugs, and unprotected sexual behaviour (Agnw, 2007). On road traffic accident, Morris and Ferguson (2007) stated that long haul truck drivers and their commercial sex contacts (women and men with whom they exchange money and /or drugs for sex) have been implicated in the increase in road traffic accidents. According to Edwards (2012), drivers that ogle while driving cause nearly one million crashes every year. Engaging in sexual activities while driving affects drivers negatively by reducing their effectiveness in handling the vehicle and impairs their judgment, thereby leading to road traffic accident (Edwards, 2012). The above literatures imply that road traffic accidents can be caused by risky sexual activities by drivers. Lack of concentration can make a driver crash other vehicles or stationary objects, and this can be as a result of engaging in sexual behaviours while driving on the road (such as fondling a girl).

Commercial vehicle drivers are drivers involved in carrying individuals and goods from one place to another. According to Tuchen, Roepstorff and Krause (2006), commercial drivers are drivers who have possessed additional testing to qualify them to drive vehicles for carrying goods or passengers. They are all individuals, whether paid or volunteer, who

* Corresponding author: Muhammad Zaharadeen Yahaya
Department of Physical and Health Education, Federal University Wukari, Taraba State.

operate commercial motor vehicles (Venderbitt, 2008). In general, commercial drivers are those that are qualified to carry goods or passengers from one destination to the other. There are different kinds of commercial vehicle driver which is dependent on the nature of their driving or the vehicle they drive. Venderbitt (2008) stated that there are drivers that are employed privately which are chauffeur; there are ones that drive trucks; there are ones that convey people and goods from one place to another called commercial vehicle drivers; and there are those that drive trains called the coachmen. The present study will be concerned with commercial vehicle drivers because they are the ones that mostly use the road thereby, are more vulnerable to road traffic accidents. WHO (2004) in a report estimated that the number of deaths due to traffic accident will increase by 65% between the years 2000 and 2020, with this figure expected to be as high as 80% in developing countries. Nigeria is among the developing countries stated above in the report. Pepple and Adio (2014) reported that in Nigeria, commercial vehicle drivers are more vulnerable to road traffic accident as a result of deplorable habits of commercial drivers from alcohol intoxication, inattentiveness and poor knowledge of traffic regulations. Other peculiar factor that can causes accident are lack of skill, knowledge of road code, over speeding, recklessness, sleeping, bad road, and obstacles on the road such as animals.

There are socio-demographic variables that influence accident causation among commercial vehicle drivers. However, this study will test marital status as factors that influence health risk behaviours of commercial motorcycle drivers in the area of the study.

This study was carried out in Jalingo, which is the capital of Taraba state. Taraba state is located at the northern part of Nigeria. People of the local government area patronize commercial drivers as means of transportation and conveying of goods round the locality.

The purpose of the study was to ascertain the health risk behaviours associated with accident causation among commercial motorcycle drivers in Jalingo L.G.A. of Taraba State. Specifically, the study seeks to ascertain if;

- Risky sexual behaviour is a factor of accident causation among commercial vehicle drivers in Jalingo L.G.A.

1.1. Research Questions

- How is risky sexual behaviour a factor of accident causation among commercial vehicle drivers in Jalingo L.G.A?

1.2. Hypothesis

One null hypotheses was postulated to guide the studies and tested at .05 level of significance.

- There is no significant relationship between risky sexual behaviours on accident causation and marital status of commercial motorcycle drivers.

2. Methodology

The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population for the study comprised all the commercial vehicle drivers in all parks in the Jalingo local government area. The population is 2,000 commercial vehicle drivers with registered with National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW). The distribution is as follows; A.J. Awoniyi main motor park (cars, 250), A.J. Awoniyi main motor park (buses, 210), A.J. Awoniyi main motor park (heavy trucks, 278), Taraba transport corp. motor park (buses, 265), Old timber motor park (taxi, 125), Nassrawo garage (tipper, 220), Jalingo main market park (taxi, 308), and Tashan Kabiru motor park (cars, 225). (Source: Office of NURTW Taraba State, 2015). The sample sizes were 160 commercial vehicle drivers. Using proportional sampling technique, 20 commercial vehicle drivers were selected each out of the 8 commercial parks in order to ensure that all types of commercial vehicle drivers are used for the study.

3. Results

3.1. Research Questions

- How is risky sexual behaviour a factor of accident causation among commercial vehicle drivers in Jalingo L.G.A?

Table 1 Risky sexual behaviour as a factor of accident causation {n=148}

Item statement	\bar{x}	SD
Risky sexual behaviour causes loss of attention among drivers	3.26	0.50
Risky sexual behaviours are detrimental to wellbeing	3.43	0.54
Ogling and romancing while driving promote distractions among drivers	3.32	0.52
It makes driver vulnerable to sexual infections	3.30	0.55
Long distances increases vulnerability to risky sexual behaviour among drivers	3.38	0.55
Cluster Mean (\bar{x})	3.35	0.53

Criterion Mean (\bar{x}) = 2.50; A factor = Cluster (\bar{x}) > Criterion (\bar{x}) Therefore, 3.35 > 2.50

Data in Table 6 Shows that the highest score was by, risky sexual behaviours are detrimental to wellbeing (\bar{x} = 3.43, SD = 0.54), followed by, long distances increase vulnerability to risky sexual behaviour among drivers (\bar{x} = 3.38, SD = 0.55), ogling and romancing while driving promote distractions among drivers (\bar{x} = 3.32, SD = 0.52) while, it makes driver vulnerable to sexual infections (\bar{x} = 3.30, SD = 0.55) and the least score of (\bar{x} = 3.26, SD = 0.50) was by, risky sexual behaviour causes loss of attention among drivers. All the items scored above the criterion mean (\bar{x}) of 2.50 and cluster mean (\bar{x}) of 3.35 which shows that risky sexual behaviours is associated with accident causation.

3.2. Hypothesis

- There is no significant relationship between risky sexual behaviours on road traffic accident and marital status of commercial motorcycle drivers.

Table 2 Summary of Linear regression on relationship between health risk behaviours (HRBs) and marital status

Model	R	R ²	Adj. R ²	Std. Er. Est.	F-value	t-value	Unstandardized Coefficients B	S.E	P-value
1	0.482	0.232	0.227	5.92825	44.097	-6.641	107.867	1.398	0.000
							-4.990	0.751	0.000

Predictors: (Constant), marital status; b. Dependent variable: Health Risk Behaviours HRBs

Table 2 shows the Summary of Linear regression of P < 0.05 significant relationship between health risk behaviours of accident causation and marital status. The R- square value of 0.232 indicates a modest relationship in that 23.2 % of the variation in health risk behaviours was explained by level of education. The F-value of 44.097 indicates that there was a significant linear relationship between health risk behaviours and marital status. This further indicates that the regression model significantly predicts health risk behaviours. The further shows that both the constant (intercept) and slope of regression line (Beta, unstandardized coefficients) was significantly different from zero at P<0.000 which is shown in the column labeled “significant“. This implies that marital status predicts health risk behaviours.

4. Discussion

The findings on Table 1 risky sexual behaviour was a factor for accident causation (\bar{x} = 3.35, SD = 0.53). The result was expected because risky sexual behaviour as observed causes loss of attention among commercial vehicle driver which can easily cause accident due to the sexual behaviour involve by most drivers such as fondly with girl while driving and also ogling and romancing while driving promote distractions among drivers. The results were in line with that of Edwards (2012), drivers that ogle while driving causes nearly one million crashes every year. Edwards (2012) further reported that engaging in sexual activities while driving affects drivers negatively by reducing their effectiveness in handling the vehicle and impairs their judgment, thereby, leading to road traffic accident.

Table 2 shows that there was no significant relationship between health risk behaviours of accident causation and marital status of commercial vehicle drivers. The finding was not expected because is the status of each individual in relation to the marriage laws or customs of the country, that is, never married, married, widowed and remarried, divorced and not married, married but legally separated and de facto union. The finding contrast with Cho, Khang and Kawachi (2008) reported that risky behaviour rates are lower for married drivers than they are for unmarried ones,

and marriage seems to be even more beneficial to men than women in this regard. This implies that married commercial vehicle drivers benefit more in the aspect of reducing or avoiding behaviours that can endanger their lives and wellbeing because of their spouses. Furthermore, Schone and Weinick (2012) reported that married adults not only appear to have better mental and physical health than their unmarried counterparts, but also have lower morbidity and mortality.

5. Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions have been drawn;

- Risky sexual behaviour was a factor for accident causation (Table 1).
- There was significant relationship between health risk behaviours of accident causation and marital status of commercial vehicle drivers (Table 2).

Recommendations

Based on the finding and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were drawn:

- Commercial vehicle park owners should not only employ qualified drivers, but as well ensure that their drivers do not indulge in risky sexual behaviour that are capable of causing road accident, this can be achieved by creating a working monitoring team.
- Also, commercial vehicle drivers caught engaging in health risk behaviour while on duty should be severely punished in order to deter others from the acts.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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